

Effect of Temperature on Coagulation Constants of Some Lyophobic Sols

D. N. Chaturvedi and O. P. Bansal

During slow coagulation of arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, nickel ferrocyanide and manganese dioxide sols with different electrolytes, the temperature effect on the constants, a , m and n of the equation

$$\frac{1}{c-a} = \frac{n}{m} t + \frac{1}{m}$$

has been studied at four temperatures. The rise in temperature has been found to cause a decrease in the values of these constants.

Bhattacharya *et al.*¹ proposed a relation between concentration of electrolyte and the corresponding time of coagulation of sols and suggested an equation :

$$\frac{1}{C-a} = \frac{n}{m} \cdot t + \frac{1}{m}$$

where ' a ', ' m ' and ' n ' are constants. Ghosh and Gangopadhyay² derived this equation theoretically at constant temperature. An attempt has been made in this paper to study the effect of temperature on the above constants, using dialysed arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, nickel ferrocyanide and manganese dioxide sols and KCl, BaCl₂ and AlCl₃ as coagulating electrolytes.

From the inflections in viscosity-time curves the values of ' t ' (i.e., time of coagulation of the sol) was determined by adding different concentrations of electrolyte, and the values of the constants ' a ', ' m ' and ' n ' were obtained using the graphical method of Bhattacharya³. The linearity of the graphs at different temperatures ranging from 25° to 40° suggests the applicability of the above equation. The values of the constants for the different sols coagulating in presence of KCl are given in table I as typical of the other electrolytes.

The rise in temperature has been found to cause a decrease in the values of these constants. The decrease in the values of a and m show that the stability of sols decreases as temperature increases. This is in accordance with the observations of Garner

1. A. K. Bhattacharya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 179; *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1955, **10**, 551; 1956, **11**, 124.
2. B. N. Ghosh and A. K. Gangopadhyay, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **386**, 811.
3. A. K. Bhattacharya, *Koll. Z.*, 1955, **141**, 95.

and Lewis⁴ and Burton and Deacon⁵. The justification of the results is confirmed by the arguments forwarded by Yadav and Verma⁶. The nature of variation of 'n', the susceptibility of the sol, cannot be predicted because of its dependence on several factors.

TABLE I

Typical values of parametric constants of Bhattacharya's equation.

Sol	Electrolyte	Temp.	a (mM/l)	m (mM/l)	n (min) ⁻¹
As ₂ S ₃ (Conc. 1.026 g/L)	KCl	25°	30.5	181	0.73
		30°	28.5	166	0.33
		35°	27.5	111	0.11
		40°	26.5	83	0.08
Sb ₂ S ₃ (Conc. 1.509 gm/L)	KCl	25°	8.5	250	1.00
		30°	7.0	222	0.44
		35°	6.0	166	0.17
		40°	4.5	153	0.15
Nickel ferrocyanide (Conc. 1.228 g/L)	KCl	25°	42	250	0.75
		30°	39	181	0.18
		35°	36	156	0.14
		40°	34	142	0.08
Manganese dioxide (Conc. 1.562 g/L)	KCl	25°	26	95	0.19
		30°	25	86	0.17
		35°	23	80	0.08
		40°	22	76	0.07

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Chemical Laboratories,
Agra College, Agra.

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5. E. F. Burton and B. R. Deacon, *Kolloid Symposium Monograph*, 1928, VI, p. 77.
6. B. P. Yadav and R. K. Verma, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 325.